

Category	Subcategory	Mapping to the patch management process	Concept	Code	Description	Number of references	Examples		
S t r a t e g y	Common strategies	All phases of the process	Frequent communication	Regular patch meetings	Bi-weekly patch meetings to discuss patching issues, find solutions, report the patching status, and measure the progress of the patch cycle.	8	[Subject - SQL Security Patching RITM# 52442] 12/7/19 - Patch meeting to be booked for 9am Friday 19th July to define requirements. 26/7/19 - [P1-BT1] putting together test run & proposal for discussion. - Win, Issue ID 1		
				Informal team discussions for complex, critical issues	Scheduling different meetings for issues that need further discussion (Shifting long standing issues to other forums for future tracking).	6	[Subject - Post-deployment issue - Data Capture servers not able to communicate with [system s1]] 7/8/20 - [P1-AT1] checking with [P2-AT2] for the other three servers that do not have a commissioning request. 21/7/20 - Set up another meeting with BT1 to discuss this request (ID 1772737). - EMR, Issue ID 42		
				Negotiation with customers about procedures and responsibilities	Getting consent for patch deployment at customers' premises, agreeing on the patch deployment dates and times, and establishing contact persons at the customer sites.	5	[Subject - Unix patching schedule confirmation] 24/7/20 - The requirements analysis revealed a major OS upgrade, not simple patching. The schedule is still being negotiated with [customer c1]. - Non-Win, Issue ID 7		
				Frequent negotiation with vendors for support	Negotiate with vendors regarding delayed patch releases and support cases.	5	[Subject - hlt100hvd001 reverting, post patch-deployment issue] 17/4/19 - Incident INC0117732 raised, need further investigation, need to troubleshoot, and organise OOB. 3/5/19 - [P1-BT1] patched, ran troubleshooting, will need to raise with Microsoft and investigate. [P2-BT1] to send info to [P3-AT2] to raise with Microsoft. 10/5 - Email sent 9/5 to [P3-AT2] with info to raise Microsoft support case. - Win, Issue ID 39		
			Collaborative decision-making	Making decisions about patch management activities	Team members making decisions about patch management tasks and task assignments.	2	[Subject - Proposal for a patch cycle change in [servers s1 and s2]] 4/4/18 - Discussions still ongoing for the decision. AT1 is still considering various options and has put them out in slides for discussion at the meeting. - EMR, Issue ID 2		
				Making decisions about task assignments		1			
			Task delegation	Task assignment	Delegating the tasks to teams/team members	21	[Subject - EPAS and .NET patching - with no upgrade of .NET version] 14/2/18 - Apps team to do due diligence and test after each night patch group in week2-3 and if any identified issues - to advise for week4 pre-prod and prod servers (pull out of patching if needed). Ownership investigation if any reported issues to be agreed - apps team as a first point? - EMR, Issue ID 3		
				Define roles and responsibilities around tasks	Well-defined roles and responsibilities around patch management activities resulting in increased accountability.	10	[Subject - Vulnerabilities in .NET Core] 21/2/20 - .NET Core is not receiving updates. A new process is required to patch this version and a service request (SR) needs to be submitted for review and assessment. [P1-BT1] to raise the SR for the issue raised by BT1 on 7th Feb 2020. - Win, Issue ID 40		
			Regularly review and update patch management process-related documentation	Regularly document patching tasks and decisions	Constantly document the decisions and activities to ease tracing back during troubleshooting post-deployment errors.	1	[Subject - New process provided for Server [sx016] but still require updates for [sx018]] 29/1/20 - Email received with manual instructions about the process. Instructions have been updated in the patching master sheet. - Win, Issue ID 54		
				Regularly update the documentation	Consistently review the documentation and test any process changes internally before updating the documentation.	2	[Subject - Update documentation for the split of [servers s1 and s2] patching into two procedures] 13/12/19 - Finalising the documentation after testing internally for handover to 24x7. 10/1/20 - Documentation to be tested in February, will be ready for handover in March. - EMR, Task ID 24		
			Vulnerability Scanning, Assessment & Prioritisation	Patch information retrieval	Set strict timelines for patch download	Report which patches are download from patch releases	Each month after "patch Tue", Org B is to provide extract to Org A of the released patches for that month and a report including what patches will be applied in the month.	1	[Subject - Provide .NET report at the start of the patch cycle] 15/3/19 - Org A requests BT1 to provide an extract of .NET released patches every month and a report including what patches will be applied to what servers [...]. - EMR, Task ID 53
				Plan alternatives for delayed patches		Classify set of patches for application		1	
						Analyse workarounds for suitability (what)	Alternatives for delayed patch releases and patching, e.g., review compliance to security when legacy systems cannot be upgraded.	3	[Subject - New 0-day vulnerability warning] 7/8/20 - The article points to an updated workaround with monthly rollout KB links, not a specific patch. 21/8/20 - Confirmation that this applies to 2012 R2, 2016 and 2008 R2. Workaround decision to be addressed in the security forum. - EMR, Issue ID 56
				Define priorities for vulnerability remediation		Assess timing of alternative remediation plans (when)	When to execute the alternative plans.	3	[Subject - Org A Change Freeze from 14th December to 12th January] 31/10/19 - Due to the change freeze in December, there will be no patching for December. 1/11/19 - AT2 wants to reserve the first two weeks of December for remediation and out-of-band patching of critical vulnerabilities as required. - Win, Task ID 34
	Prioritisation based on patch severity and impact	Prioritising patches based on severity (vulnerability risk assessment) and its impact.				11	[Subject - LDAP GPO issues] 15/5/20 - GPO creation required for testing. Proceed with GPO creation part of the request so servers can be tested before wider rollout. DCs to be updated progressively with communication to Org A's ICT and Apps teams for verification. 12/6/20 - GPO updates to proceed again next week and creation of new GPOs required to be done first. 26/06 - This has taken a backseat due to critical patches being addressed as a priority. - Win, Issue ID 85		
	Patch Testing			Prioritisation based on patch type	Prioritising patches based on the patch type.	4	[Subject - OS security patches need to be tracked separated in the vulnerability remediation] 15/5/20 - [P1-AT1] requesting the OS security patches to be tracked separately to all other vulnerability remediation. Org B's report should only be addressing OS security patches anyway but can make sure to separate any non-OS remediation tasks. - EMR, Task ID 45		
				Develop security compliance policies	Compliance with security standards before deployment.	5	[Subject - [s1] new servers compliance] 4/12/18 - This item remains open until all new [s1] servers are fully compliant including security hardening prior to being pushed into production and support. 18/2/18 - Security approved the new [s1] servers, go-live completed on 18/2. - EMR, Task ID 1		
	Modify software configurations and			Develop contingency plans for test failures	Develop contingency plan for test failures	Preparing plan B for patch testing errors.	4	[Subject - EPAS and .NET patching - with no upgrade of Net version] 14/2/18 - As discussed with the security team, EPAS17.3 Pre-Prod and Prod will go into 2-monthly cycle, starting March. Non-Prod will continue monthly. Plan is to move all EPAS 17.3 to monthly patching after 3 consecutive successful cycles. Success criteria = no business impact AND no major .NET version upgrades (e.g., updates within the .NET version). If any issues are identified after due diligence and testing, week4 pre-prod and prod servers to be pulled out of patching. - EMR, Issue ID 3	
					Pre-investigation of requisites		2	[Subject - Registry key missing for Knowledge Base (KB) ID in LDAP] 2/10/20 - Patches not installed on [servers s1 and s2] due to missing a registry key. [P1-BT1] to check settings and apply where missing. - Win, Task ID 24	
				Patch pre-requisites investigation	Set up the required requisites for patch deployment.	2	[Subject - March Pre-requisite Investigation relating to OS Patching] 17/4/20 - 3 new SSU pre-requisites to be applied. Updates have been populated on the SharePoint, but servers identified will be rectified as part of normal monthly patching cycle. 29 Servers currently require this patch and no registry changes or reboots required. 16 servers were flagged as auto and changed to semi auto to confirm application of the patches. Remaining 13 were manual. - Win, Issue ID 79		
					Identify the dependency changes	Identify and prepare the required dependencies for patch deployment.	2	[Subject - OCS Dependencies & Risks] 28/6/19 - Information required from OCS around any dependencies and risks of security patching (OS) to progress with patching. - Non-Win, Issue ID 2	

Issues

Strategies specific to each phase of the process	Patch Deployment	continguous and dependencies	Modify the configurations	Change the configurations to suit patch deployment.	1	[Subject - GPO creations (configs) to be done together] 12/6/20 - [P1-BT1] to create new GPOs at the same time early next week in preparation for the next round of additions for vulnerability remediation. - Win, Task ID 49
		Timely coordination of patch deployment schedules	Planning patch windows	Planning when to patch.	8	[Subject - Review of [s1] servers' patch windows: re-balancing and extended windows proposed] 13/3/19 - Org B proposes 4-hour windows starting at 18:00 each night. The first lot of servers to start Friday week 2 after the "Patch Tuesday". Proposal provided for Org A's consideration. - Win, Task ID 9
Establish contact roles during and post-deployment for verification	Defining who will contact the external parties to confirm the deployment.		6	[Subject - Scheduled deployment at hospital [h1]] 24/1/19 - [P1-BT1] to ensure phone call after patching is completed tonight for [server s1]. 7/2/19 - Information provided this morning for build process to commence. - EMR, Issue ID 34		
Planning load balance	Planning the spread of servers evenly through patch windows (how to patch).		5	[Subject - Review of [s1] server's patch windows - rebalancing & extended windows proposed] 11/1/19 - Need to move back the start time for [s1] servers patching to "patch Tue" + 2days @21:00. For this we need to review the current schedule, agree on new extended patch windows (proposed 4-6 hrs windows) and to spread servers evenly through the windows. Ongoing work - for consideration by Org A once the new patch windows are clarified. 31/5/19 - Email directly to [P1-AT4] to advise that the change can be accommodated while awaiting 4h window approval and overall rebalancing approach approval. - Win, Issue ID 14		
Apply workarounds to maximise service availability	Cluster-based patching (based on patch types)		Configuring the group settings and deployment of the patch clusters for higher availability.	7	[Subject - Patch deployment failed at [server s1]] 24/1/18 - Single point of failure for [server s1]. AT1 to review the proposed design for clustering for high availability. Currently hard to obtain reboot timings and only one reboot is allowed. Ask the customer for an extended window and move the patching to the weekend. - Win, Task ID 6	
	Extend patch windows for critical patches with multi reboots		Planning extended windows for patches that required multi reboots in out-of-band windows.	4	[Subject - Smartlink Servers extended patch windows] 31/5/19 - OOB patch needed to catch up. [P1-AT1] to advise the window, may need longer window (5-6 hrs suggested) and multi reboot. Note: Server [s1] is not under support. 14/6/19 - OOB patching completed, reintroduced to standard schedule. - EMR, Issue ID 20	
	Balancing the load on servers		Balancing the load on servers during deployment to reduce service unavailability.	4	[Subject - Auto Rebalancing required] 3/10/19 - Optimal amount per window for auto patching is 32 servers. 8/10/19 - The spreadsheet sent to [P1-AT2] and [P2-AT5] for redistribution. 18/10 - Review in progress. 31/10 - [P3-BT1] suggesting maximum limit of servers per window is 32 per 4-hour block, client looking at which windows can shuffle. - Win, Issue ID 57	
	Pre-load the patches offline to avoid exceeding patch windows		Pre-loading the patches offline to avoid patch deployment exceeding the allocated patch window.	1	[Subject -Pre-download for auto patching required by management] 31/10/19 - Org B is expecting formal NSSR from Org A - T2 to advise that pre-staging of patches or downloading "earlier" than the patching window to allow earlier patch download/multi-reboots. Org B is suggesting patches can be predownloaded on week 2 Thursday as there is no patching on that day. - Win, Issue ID 53	
	Separate patch windows for failover patching		Maintaining backup servers to concurrently run the services while being rebooted.	2	[Subject - Request to change the patch window of HLT667U003] 11/4/19 - Currently set to 0000-0300, but the full backup of server patching happening during this window which causes slowness/issues with patching. Suggest changing the window to 0600-0900. - Win, Issue ID 36	
	Manual deployment for complex patches to minimise damage		Redeployment of failed patching for unknown reasons	Redeployment of erroneous patches.	7	[Subject - Post-deployment error at [server s1] causing the printing service unavailable] 31/10/19 - This server was patched on 18/10 at 2 am-6 am. Due to the errors, patching will be done manually in November. - Win, Issue ID 6
Manual patching of business critical servers			Manual patching for business-critical servers (e.g., life support machines).	3	[Subject - Software version issues on some servers] Issues with 47 Office patches on [server s1]-5 (multi-languages and x32 and x64 bit versions) and 7 Visual Studio related patches on SCMPRODPCPMW001. 24/1/19 - A ticket raised for [server s1] for Org B to investigate Visual Studio patches and manually apply if required. 3/8/19 - Patches are installed by [P1-BT1] as OOB with [change request ch1]. This item can be closed now. - EMR, Issue ID 11	
Manual patching of complex legacy systems		Manually patching legacy software systems.	2	[Subject - 2008 patching update] 18/11/20 - Currently down to 11 servers out of the 273 with patching issues. It'll be a manual patching in OOB. Also, someone will be sitting there watching to rectify if any issues arise during the deployment. - EMR, Issue ID 69		
Agile deployment for executing changes	Execute complex patch deployment changes in small iterations	This is done as a precautionary measure and to build confidence around the changes. Also, because a change in the patching process could create devastating consequences.	6	[Subject - Review of patch cycle timings] 22/2/18 - Org A is considering going for bi-monthly deployment cycles for .NET patching and then move to monthly deployment after the confidence is built. - EMR, Task ID 2		
Post-Deployment Patch Verification	Establish post-deployment verification procedures	Verification through gathering client feedback	Define set of procedures for post-deployment patch verification (how to verify).	4	[Subject - Automated second rescan for reboots] 31/10/19 - [P1-BT1] raised this issue, he has configured the window to rescan for missing patches and conduct a second reboot if required. No issues during patching, seeking client feedback for verification. - EMR, Task ID 28	
		Verification through monitoring		2	[Subject - Tracking of GPO applications not intended] 24/07 - Rollback status: no reported issue due to the rollout, rollback not required at this point. Keep monitoring for one more week. - Win, Issue ID 91	
		Verification through analysis of log system status		2	[Subject - SQL tlogs and IIS logs on C drives - capacity issue] 22/2/19 - Org B to run report of servers that have any SQL or IIS logs/data on C drive and provide to [P1-AT2]. Then, apps teams to look at moving off C. - Win, Issue ID 19	
		Verification through periodic scans		2	[Subject - Internal DXC server vulnerabilities] 20/3/20 - The scans identified application vulnerabilities on internal Org B's Jump hosts. The remediation is being investigated. - Non-Win, Issue ID 15	
	Collectively handle post-deployment issues	Find workarounds for failed deployments (countermeasures)	Workarounds such as Out-Of-Band (OOB) patching to catch up with missing patches, reverting back installed erroneous patches, and uninstalling EOL and unnecessary software.	6	[Subject - Tracking of GPO applications that are not intended] 10/7/20 - Information sent to [P1-AT2] and [P2-AT2]. Patch [p1] will need a rollback. 24/7/20 - Rollback executed, no reported issue due to the rollback. Keep open for one more meeting for monitoring. - Win, Task ID 51	
		Investigation of root causes (troubleshooting)	Identify the root causes for issues identified post-deployment.	3	[Subject - Issue with Print Servers Patching] 16/10/20 - [P1-BT1] did some investigation and it was found that a KB was missing in one server. Since this KB is only for 2016 server, it is inapplicable. Need verification on that [P1-AT5] to double check on the vulnerabilities scan. - Win, Issue ID 54	
	Document deployment status of every patch	Document the status of each task	Record the status of each patch in the Patching Tracker.	3	[Subject - [Servers s1 and s2] successfully patched] 24/7/20 - [...] No further issues experienced since patching. Manual instructions and deployment status updated in the shared tracker. Will be kept in-monitor for another couple of weeks. - EMR, Issue ID 47	